

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PHILOSOPHY AND DEVELOPMENT: DEMONSTRATING THEIR CONVERGENCE AND AFFINITY

Paul Olorunsola Folorunso

PhD.,

Department of Philosophy,

Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State Nigeria.

Abstract

This paper tackles one of the main problems that contemporary philosophers grapple with. This is the question of the contemporary relevance of philosophy, especially to human and societal development. Often times, one hears cynical and sarcastic questions like, Can philosophy bake bread? Of what use is philosophy to development? How may philosophical insights and prowess be useful for human and societal development? This paper responds to these and other like interrogations with the critical tool of hermeneutics and comparative analytic method. Inter alia, the paper reveals that the ultimate teleology of philosophical engagements, critical and reflective reflections is to achieve sustainable human and societal development. Consequently, the paper concludes that to advance an integral development of man and society; philosophy must be reverentially appealed to as a competent tool for authentic and sustainable development. The paper is a qualitative research and relies on secondary data for its conceptual critical analysis.

Keywords: Development, Hermeneutics, Philosophy, Society, Sustainable Development.

Introduction

In philosophical studies, one finds many course titles that read, 'philosophy of X- philosophy of this or that'. For instance, we have courses like philosophy of education, philosophy of law, philosophy of physical sciences, philosophy of natural sciences, philosophy of nursing, philosophy of literature and a host of other second order disciplines. The first and rudimentary idea one infers from these course titles is that philosophy is interfacing with this specific subjects or disciplines. But what are the basic assumptions and justification for philosophy's and philosopher's interface with these 'independent' subject matters and disciplines? The usage of the phrase or predicate "philosophy of X" denoting any applied philosophical courses implies that what is predicated (concept, phenomenon, events or discipline) could be competently interrogated or critically probed by philosophy. This also implies that philosophy has a business relationship with the subject matter of its interrogation. Philosophy by this relationship and its critical nature has the capacity and competence to enquire about the specific nature, the method, the scope, significance, meaning and the socio-cognitive usage of the entity that constitutes its subject of investigation and interrogation (Uzomah, 2018, 12). On this basis, the copulation or conjugation of philosophy and development strongly indicates that these germane concepts have strong bonds or nexus.

Consequently, the thrust of this paper is to substantiate the relationship between philosophy and development. In addition, this association may also suggest that philosophy has the competence to interrogate the concept, phenomenon and issues of development. The paper also attempts to deductively establish what role(s) philosophy and philosophers play towards the attainment of authentic and sustainable development of man and society for the advancement and improvement of human existence and living conditions.

Ideally, every human attempt towards development principally aims at improving man's experience and wellbeing for the attainment of happiness which is his supreme pursuit. Every developmental effort of humans is targeted towards the survival and comfort of humans on earth; and ever since the first family of humans walked and worked on the surface of the earth; ever since humans started living in societies, their pre-occupations has always been to make life bearable and comfortable for their ultimate happiness.

In pursuance, the per inter-alia, further argues that philosophy has the gut and competence to ruminate on issues pertaining to development on the account that, as a genuine science of human existence and a critical quest for truth, philosophy is a critical quest for the advancement of human condition and meaningful living. Of course, development essentially and functionally configured presupposes the improvement and advancement of the conditions and quality of the living conditions of man, for the betterment of human existence and experience in the society. If philosophy as a critical human endeavour is ultimately preoccupied by development of man and society, then, philosophy has the competence to critically engage every developmental efforts and strides of man to ascertain their significance to man and society (physical and social environments), especially at this auspicious moment in the history of humanity when the delicate state of the eco system has made it imperatively opt for sustainable development (Uzomah and Folorunso, 2023, 60). Moreover, because philosophy studies man from his ontological and integral perspective, philosophy understands the nature of man, his essence, his teleology in the society, etc. and as such, philosophy is well-equipped with the capacity and disposition to authentically establish what development should be for man. The proper concept of sustainable development may be properly conceptualized in the tradition of philosophy as a supreme science that studies and conceptualizes reality as one integrated and

harmonious whole (Uzomah and Folorunso, 60). Invariably, philosophy's notion of genuine development would be an eco-friendly or bio-centric development. Eco-friendly or bio-centric development has the propensity of ensuring the continual improvement of the quality of life and living standard of extant and future generations and the continual survival of the earth home to biodiversity. With this preamble, the paper is now poised to reflect on what is implied by philosophy of development and what philosophy got to do with development.

Philosophy and Development

The term 'Philosophy and Development' or 'Philosophy of Development' which places philosophy and development side by side suggests that philosophy and development have a relationship. In other words, the keyword that permeates the phrase "Philosophy of Development" is the "relationship". In this regard, placing philosophy and development side by side in the phrase, "philosophy of development" presupposes that philosophy maintains some sort of relationship with development (Uzomah, 11-12). The great and thoughtful question that ensues here and begs for an incisive response is, what is it about development that elicits the curious and investigative inquest of philosophy? Put differently, what is philosophy after in development? Or, what are those issues germane to development that are attractive to or inspire philosophy's investigative and analytic attention or normative intervention? These questions enquire about the inextricable bond existing between philosophy and development.

The Relationship between Development and Philosophy

The following are some of the practical explications of the affinity and convergence of philosophy and development:

1. All Existential Human Concerns Including Development is the Priority of Philosophy

The first point of relationship between the duo (s) is that development is first and foremost an existential human concern; and if development is of paramount human concern, it is equally the concern of philosophy. Whatever aspect of human concern development is, it is equally the business of philosophy. Every human existential concern is crucial to philosophy because philosophy was given birth to by existential and overwhelming human and social concerns. In lieu, so long there is always the possibility of having human concerns; philosophy will never cease to exist. Philosophy defined as man's critical quest for a meaningful living, reflectively engages every human concern to make meaningful and advance human existence and experience in the universe (Uzomah, 12). Hence, philosophy is not only important but essential to developmental studies and strides. If man's developmental concern can be properly address, it must be done in the light of philosophy.

2. Development is (a) Critical Human Phenomenon

One of the most fundamental connections between development and philosophy is that the concept 'development' is a critical phenomenon that impacts directly on human existence and experience in the society; and

every problem that has either direct or indirect impact on human existence and development is the concern of philosophy. Human existence, development and flourishing are the linchpin of philosophical discourse (Uzomah and Folorunso, 61-62). To this extent, philosophy and development have the same object. To properly address the problems of human and societal development philosophical doctrines, perspectives, approaches and prescriptions must be aptly adopted and utilized.

3. Development is for Humans and Humans are the Prime Subject of Philosophy

Development in all its aspects and perspectives is a human endeavour prosecuted by man and for the benefit of man. In this light, man is the fulcrum and measure of genuine development. More fundamentally, every authentic development ought to promote man's essence and supreme good in the society for an integral development of the whole human person. The point of relationship here is first and foremost, philosophy is for humans and humans are the prime subject of philosophy. Second, philosophy by its ontological investigative approach quite understands man's essence and supreme good (Uzomah, 13). Moreover, philosophy understands man's composite nature and the supreme value of maintaining hypostatic unity in the study and development of man. Hence, authentic development consists of the harmonious and integral transformation of the whole powers of man. Consequently, this sagacity and privileged disposition of philosophy makes it not just a suitable co-traveler, but an inevitable and valuable *sine qua non* of development (Uzomah and Folorunso, 62-63). The thesis is, to advance an integral development of man and society; philosophy must be reverentially appealed to as a competent tool for authentic development. In other words, if development is for humans and philosophy is for humans and humans are the prime object of philosophy, it therefore means that philosophy and development are internally related in terms of their subject.

Another dimension of integral development that expresses the existential and essential relationship between development and philosophy is the fact that, integral or holistic development consists in the progressive and harmonious advancement of the cultural, social, economic, political, religious/spiritual, etc. lives of man. And these aspects of man's life are critical subject matters of philosophical investigations (Jacob, 24). Philosophy studies them strictly in relation to man's ontological essence. Based on this understanding, philosophy becomes categorically imperative to achieving integral development. Integral development understood as that development that harmoniously advances all aspects of man's life and experience in the society in accordance to human nature and social essence.

Moreover, philosophy understands the concept of justice, especially as it relates to equitable distribution of opportunities and commonwealth for the common good of all in the society (Jacob, 50). The extent of a nation's development is measured by how much it has improved the life, wellbeing and living condition of her teeming population. Philosophy makes us understand

that development properly conceived and conceptualized must be oriented towards common good. All must be involved in the plan and strategies for development, and accordingly all must ensure the fruits of development (Uzomah, 14). In this sense, an equitable and just concept and conceptualization of development is such that development is of the people, from the people and for the people. This concept and conceptualization of development reprimands and nullifies sectional and parochial development.

3. Man's Developmental Activities Profoundly Influence Nature

The Prerogative of Philosophy is the Conservation of the Harmony in and of Nature. Philosophy and development are also related in the sense that both are critically linked to nature, the only platform and habitat for human dwelling and survival (Adewale, 45). Developmental activities if not properly planned and executed might have profound implication to the symbiotic relationship existing between humans and biodiversity that is responsible for the essential harmony and balance in nature (Uzomah and Folorunso, 64). To ensure this essential balance, it is the prerogative of philosophy to always interface with humanity to order her craving for development to align it with nature so as to ensure sustainable development.

The Need for Sustainable Development

It is an expression of an irrefutable fact that man's aggressive developmental activities have profound impacts that are sometimes precarious to nature, home to humanity and other members of the community of biodiversity. This makes development another fundamental problem of human existence and experience. "The most important systemic risk we face today is climate change. The reality is proving worse than scientists had foreseen. Climate change is running faster than we expected and political will unfortunately, is slowing down" (<https://www.un.org/press/en/2019/sgsm19468.doc.htm>). In the most recent time, a practical phenomenon that brutally demonstrated the consequences of man's destructive developmental activities was when Western Europe was smashed by high Heat wave. On the 24th and 26th of July, 2019 Western Europe recorded highest heat wave; with Germany 42.6, France 42.6, UK 38.1. They in recorded history experienced an all-time record heat wave. This according to scientist is the hottest temperature in recorded time since 1833. This is going to become a new normal.

Although most great economies, especially America, because of economic reason are obstinately denying the existence of climate change, however, this problem is no less urgent. It is expedient to philosophy owing to the very fact that human life and existence inexorably depends on nature for its survival and flourishing. Man inevitably needs nature to meaningfully exist and survival, but nature does not require man to either exist nor to survive. This is to say that man's destructive tendencies toward nature attract ineluctable repercussions (Uzomah and Folorunso, 65). Hence, any injury to nature wrought by man's aggressive quest for development is inescapably a profound injury to human existence. The nature of the expediency of philosophy's

concern against man's destructive control over nature is manifested in the fact that within philosophical studies, two independent, yet interrelated second order interdisciplinary philosophical disciplines are dedicated to the interrogation of the implications of man's inordinate activities on the environment (nature). These disciplines include, Environmental Philosophy and Environmental Ethics. Hence, the business relationship philosophy or duty philosophy has with development is to ensure that man's developmental activities respect natural rhythms and harmonies, protect the sanctity of biodiversity and ensure that man maintains a symbiotic relationship with nature (Uzomah and Folorunso, 65). In other words, philosophy's inextricable relationship with development is to engender the brand of development that is eco-friendly for the immediate end of ensuring the health and safety of nature, and ultimately for the useful living and future survival and flourishing of man.

The essence of environmental ethics and philosophy is to ensure sustainable development. Sustainable development as formally defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WECD) is "development that meets the needs of the people today without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (cited in Uzomah, 45). It can also be defined as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (*Environmental Solutions*, 2005, 66). The concept of needs goes beyond simply material needs and includes values, relationships, freedom to think, act, and participate, all amounting to sustainable living, morally, and spiritually (Ibid.). It also extends to gender equality and parity and the need to establish a just and egalitarian society. The concept of sustainable development has undergone various developmental phases since its introduction. The historical development of the concept saw participation of various organizations and institutions, which nowadays work intensely on the implementation of its principles and objectives. The concept has experienced different critiques and interpretations over the time while being accepted in different areas of human activity and the definition of sustainable development has become one of the most cited definitions in the literature (cited in Uzomah, 45). According to the document *Environmental Solutions*:

The 30-year journey of four World Summits from Stockholm to Nairobi to Rio and to Johannesburg has put the world on notice that achieving sustainable development in the twenty-first century is not an option but an imperative.... The 1972 UN conference in Stockholm highlighted the concerns for preserving and enhancing the environment and its biodiversity to ensure human rights to a healthy and productive world. The developing countries argued that their priority was development, whereas the developed countries made a case for environmental protection and conservation as the prime issue... In 1983 the United Nations Commission on Environment and Development was created and in 1987, the Commission issued the Brundtland Report. This report highlighted that equity, growth, and environmental maintenance are simultaneously possible

and that each country is capable of achieving its full economic potential while at the same time enhancing its resource base. It emphasized three fundamental components to sustainable development: environmental protection, economic growth, and social equity (cited in Uzomah, 47).

Although, there are several or diverse ways of conceptualizing the concept of sustainable development; however, the point of convergence of definitions of sustainable development is the realization and recommendation that humanity has the duty to ensure that the quality of life of humans should not decline over the long-term future. The duty of humans is to ensure that its developmental strides and feats should continually improve the quality of the life of present generation and also guarantee the good and qualitative life of the future generations. The present generation must not mortgage the survival and happiness of the future generation in their aggressive quest for development. Ultimately, the idea of sustainable development prescribes that those living in the present has the categorical duty to ensure that in the use of natural resources, in the creative use of technology to interact with nature and in pursuing progress of any sort, the quality of life and survival of those living in the present and those to live in the future is guaranteed. This encapsulates the ethical principle of intergenerational responsibility which enjoins the present generation to protect and preserve the common heritage and patrimony of humanity for future generation.

Consequently, the concept of sustainable development is a germane issue to philosophy and as such, justifies the essential link between development studies and philosophy. Philosophy's interface and postulations on issues of development is rationally well-founded. If philosophy cannot concern itself with this issue that is profoundly crucial to humanity's perpetual existence; what then is the use philosophy?

The Audacity and Competence of Philosophy to Interrogate Human Endeavours and Fundamental Existential Issues

It is noteworthy to state that, apart from the relationship that philosophy has with specific subject matters or disciplines or issues it studies, that justifies its dynamic interface and critical normative interventions; philosophy's dynamic and critical interface with other disciplines is warranted by its very nature and the object of its inquest. Philosophy is by nature critical and critically pursues truth as its essential object. By truth, we mean truth about all of reality in its physical and metaphysical dimensions. The critical nature and the pursuit of truth of philosophy make it a competent investigator of development. Also, philosophy's insistence on good, coherent and sound reasoning makes it qualified to interrogate issues of development. Philosophy has the legitimacy and effective framework to probe into the nature, method, scope and the socio-cognitive meaning of development (Uzomah, 15). Of course, what provides philosophy with this privileged disposition is the fact that philosophy is not just a speculative reasoning but also an existential critical program.

Another factor that empowers philosophy to critically and normatively engage development is the limitless scope of philosophy. Every human endeavour, all that concerns reality and human existence, so long they can be logically thought, taught and expressed are within the ambience of what philosophy has the competence to critically interrogate. And development is one of such items that philosophy can critically interrogate. Moreover, "The epistemic, metaphysical and ethical values of philosophy not only form the basis of people's lives and undertakings they also provide the foundation on which the edifice of knowledge in various academic disciplines is built (Nwinya, p. 1.). Based on this tokenism, philosophy is well grounded to critically interrogate issues, states of affairs, phenomena as they relate and affect man in his social and physical environment.

The fact that development concerns or defines the harmonious and progressive advancement of all realities pertaining to man's tangible and intangible existence and experiences in the society make it incumbent on philosophy which forms the basis of people's lives and undertakings to critically interface with development and development studies towards achieving integral and sustainable development (Uzomah and Folorunso, 69). Moreover, every human discipline and study is targeted towards the understanding, advancement and betterment of the life of man on earth. As a second order discipline and the science qua sciences, philosophy proceeds where these specific and individual sciences end their specific studies and developmental strides. Philosophy is an essential tool for an authentic wellbeing and profound existence. A philosopher also endeavours to increase the standard and quality of life, not only for himself but for the society at large. Seen in this perspective, the philosopher reflects on man's problems and proffers ways to solve them (Uzomah and Folorunso, 69). Simply put, the vowed aim of philosophy is development. Based on this import, philosophy of development is a reflective thinking on issues bordering on human and societal development. Consequently, a master or parent discipline that is critical in nature and one that critically pursues truth of its object and subject of investigation and indeed the truth of reality; philosophy forms the basis of people's lives and also provides the foundation of all human episteme, knowledge and undertakings, as such, philosophy is fundamentally competent to critically and normatively interface and postulate on issues concerning development, in terms of the concept, meaning, nature and essence of development to human existence, survival and flourishing.

What is Philosophy of Development?

Philosophy of development simply defined is the dynamic application of the critical tools of philosophy to critically interrogate issues of development. It is a critical analysis as well as normative intervention whose teleology is to critically and coherently analyze the concept, meaning and nature of development (Uzomah and Folorunso, 70). As a normative intervention, its vowed objective is to postulate on what the ideal concept and essence of development ought to be to ensure a proper conceptualization of development in

terms of integral and sustainable development. In other words, philosophy of development is the critical study of development in the critical and holistic tradition of philosophy in order to foster a meaningful understanding of development only in terms of integral and sustainable development.

The following questions feature prominently in philosophical discourses on development; what are the factors that are essential to the definition of development? Who sets the paradigm for defining development? Is there limit to human and societal development? What role does culture play either as a catalyst or a clog on the wheel of development? Do animals and other non-human elements in nature have rights that must not be bridge by man's developmental strides and activities? Where must man place the community of biodiversity in his plan, strategy and developmental activities? Another question may be added, is development an objective or relative concept? In other words, one may enquire if development is a process or a level?

Philosophy of development, being an interdisciplinary course is critical, reflective, analytic, expository, evaluative and normative. It reflects on the basic assumptions and propositions of the theories of development, critically analyses them to expose their underlying facts and their philosophical basis. It reflectively interrogates the reasonableness of these theories by offering critical evaluation to review whether in the bid to pursue aggressive development, various nations and their peoples adhere to the principle of fairness, solidarity and subsidiarity. Finally, through its normative nature, philosophy of development prescribes certain principles as norms that each nation must imbibe to foster genuine, integral, healthy and sustainable development, in other to foster just and good national and transnational trade relations (Uzomah, 18-19). The ultimate aim of philosophy of development is to enunciate a concept of development that aligns with the nature and essence of human existence and a concept of development that is sustainable for the continual existence, survival, flourishing and advancement of the quality of life and living standard of humanity in the present and in the future.

Thrust and Purpose of Philosophy of Development

It would not be out of place to make a bold and categorical statement that there is a significant misconception about the most important aspect of development. Owing to the critical nature of philosophy according to the analytic tradition, it is the task of philosophers to clarify misconceptions and ambiguities in theories and assumptions. Ludwig Wittgenstein in his "Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus", asserted that the "object of philosophy is the logical clarification of thoughts "so that" the result of philosophy is not a number of philosophical propositions, but to make proposition clear" (Cited in Stumpf and Fieser, 417. 72). In the light of this philosophical illumination, it behooves to assert that the most important and most fundamental of all development is that of the mind. It is the development of the whole man himself. The most important of all development is the cultivation of the mind. For all other kinds of development like social, religious, political,

technological are dependent on that of the mind (a detailed explication of this was presented in chapter two). Consequently, the philosopher, ought to consider development from this integral or holistic perspective. Not just development, but development of the whole man, and development of the whole facets, institutions, segments, practices and values of the human society. Another important observation that must be made is that since the philosopher investigates reality in its totality, he should not be wary to establish that in man's quest for development, he ought to be necessarily constrained by ethical principles.

First, philosophy of development asserts that every nation of the world in their aggressive quest for development should recognize the right of other nations. Therefore, they must in charity not champion their development at the expense of the weaker countries. The principle of solidarity and subsidiarity, mutual respect and charity must be the governing principles guiding all nations in their bid to foster integral and sustainable development of their respective nations. These concerns become imperative because a study of the four major theories of development reveals that the 'strong' or 'First World' nations in the history of development have always unjustly taken advantage of the 'weak' or 'Third World' nations. The giant nations have always been involved in an evil alliance or have continually engaged in hashing the conspiracy to prosecute their developmental strides at the expense of the weak or developing nations. Little wonder then, scholars like Edward Blyden in his "Stolen Legacy", Walter Rodney in his thesis of "How Europe Underdeveloped Africa", and a host of other scholars talked about the infamous parasitic relationship Europe established with Africa. Ultimately, this reprehensible conspiracy aims at making the third world countries to remain underdogs. To forestall this, it is the duty of the philosopher to review the covert and overt motif underlying national and transnational trades and foreign policies.

In the light of the above, Philosophy of Development is an ethical philosophy. It is a philosophy that subjects development and attempts by nations to develop their nations to critical probing or appraisal to ensure that in charity, stronger nations do not develop at the expense of other nations. For instance, according to DW News, US and China produce up to half Co2 That saturates out atmosphere (DW News, August 8, 2019. 73). Philosophy of development appraises the moral significance of such inordinate phenomenal against the sideline that while these countries enjoin the fruit of this malevolent stride, the entire world inexorably suffers its attendant consequences.

Moreover, the philosopher reflects on extant theories of development to ascertain their philosophical significance. In other words, philosophy of development examines these theories, their propositions and assumptions to ascertain if they are accurate and objective representations of the growth and advancements of nations in the course of time. Also, philosophy of development concerns itself with the task of establishing whether these theories are race and colour bias. By this understanding, it is the task of Philosophy of Development to reveal whether they infamously project the cultures,

values and innovations of certain nations as superior, to downplay other nations. Again, it is its task to ascertain whether they project the developmental pattern of a given nation or continent as a paradigm or yardstick to define development. Hence, apart from being analytic and expository, Philosophy of Development more importantly is evaluative and normative. The philosophy of development is poised to ask questions like, what are the factors that are essential to the definition of development? Who sets the paradigm for defining development? Is there limit to human and societal development? What role does culture play either as a catalyst or a clog on the wheel of development? Do animals and other non-human elements in nature have rights that must not be bridge by man's developmental strides and activities? Where must man place the community of biodiversity in his plan, strategy and developmental activities? Etc. These are some of the questions that dictate and influence the thrust and purpose of philosophy of development.

Second, it is the task of the philosopher, who interrogates development to assert that the ecosystem is a habitat to bio diversities. Man must recognize that other life forms have right to exist in the planet earth, hence, man in his quest for development must not endanger their lives. He must not also jeopardize man's future existence in the planet earth in the name of development. The unlimited drive for development pursued via technology and industrialization has continually place the earth, home to biodiversity in a delicate state. We are now at a critical moment in earth's history, we must choose the future (Uzomah and Folorunso, 73). A practical evidence of this is the most recent Western Europe's smash by the highest temperature in recorded history. The future holds great peril and promise, as the world increasingly becomes interdependent, we must realize that in the midst of the magnificent diversity of cultures and life's forms, we are one human family, one earth's community and one destiny. In this tone, philosophy of development displays its interdisciplinary nature, for it is a philosophy that shows the interplay of environmental philosophy and environmental ethics (Uzomah and Folorunso, 73).

One of the pertinent issues that necessitate philosophy of development was pointed out by A. F. Alafen who plausibly opined:

Human transcendental powers seem to have no limit, and so is human knowledge. This transcendence is what makes it possible for man to employ the services of the environment for his convenience and comfort. This is environmental domestication. However, as domestication takes place, it is followed by the consequence of degradation when maintenance and constructive measures are not put in place. This leads to environmental degradation. Man seems not to be able to survive without the environment, while on the other hand, the environment does not seem to depend on man for its continual survival (A. F. Alafen, 1).

Hence, the aggressive drive for development typified in industrialization and urbanization seems oblivious of this brute fact. Genuine development must be explorative of nature and not exploitative or corrosive of nature. In the event when it inadvertently exploits, there

must be restorative and renewable measures to forestall mortal damage to Mother Nature.

In view of the above, the most prominent question that features in environmental philosophy is, can one properly understand the relationship between the natural world and human technology and development? In the same vein, environmental ethics focuses on questions like, what should be the proper relationship between human beings and the natural world (the natural world understood in the context of biodiversity)? In the quest for development, what are those responsibilities or obligations man must have towards nature. The ultimate object of environmental ethics is how to properly balance the needs of man with his interest. These two sub-ethics examine the impact of man's developmental activities via urbanization and industrialization on the environment. They set rules or ethical codes that must refrain man from causing mortal harm to nature. In this regard, philosophy of development that shares the ultimate objective of environmental and philosophy and environmental ethics is eco-centric and normative in nature.

The ultimate essence of philosophy of development's critical review of the impact or resultant consequences of man-nature interactions in man's developmental activities is to assert the categorical imperative of sustainable development. It is the only notion or paradigm development that will ensure the continual advancement of the quality of life of both the present and future generation and the continual survival of humanity. If the natural rhythm and mechanisms of self-restoration and conservation is destabilized by the destructive developmental activities of man, and nature becomes hostile the continual survival and existence of man would be mortally jeopardized. Consequently, the ideal of sustainable development is not merely an option but fundamentally imperative.

Against this backdrop, philosophy which considers being in its totality has the competence to sensitize humanity that eco-centric approach to development is not only essential to man, but expedient for the continual existence, survival and flourishing of mankind. Philosophy of development provides for a holistic and integral approach towards development because for man to enjoy real and authentic development, he must be in harmony with nature (Uzomah and Folorunso, 76). Any attempt towards development that destabilizes the relative harmony and tranquility in nature is a reverse development. Such development could be properly classified as a negative development.

Consequently, one of the purposes of Philosophy of Development is to examine the moral issues in man's relation with his environment in his aggressive quest for development with the intent to raise conscionable and plausible solutions to these moral challenges. Philosophical studies in development must be apt to point out that "domestication deteriorates into degradation when conservative and preservative measure are not set up to check man's destructive activities towards nature. To avert this, it is expedient to employ the Kantian basic ethical framework to suggest that man must begin to see himself as a co-tenant that has a symbiotic relationship with other entities of the ecosystem and thus,

must contribute to ecosystem balance. This necessary outlook is hinged in the fact that what we do with other entities around us- man and the natural environment is determined by the value we place on it (Ibid, p. 1.).

A very crucial issue that is germane to discourses in development that is snowballing into crisis is the phenomenon of the huge tones of wastes, especially plastic waste generated globally as a result of the overwhelming dependence on industrial goods. The large portion of this waste is bio-non-degradable. They are found littered at the nooks and crannies of big towns and villages globally. Most of these wastes find their ways into drainages and eventually in the seas. They block drainages thereby causing erosion. In the sea, they pollute the sea thereby threatening aquatic lives (Uzomah and Folorunso, 76-77). This sort of development is not a sustainable development because it is not environmentally friendly.

On the strength of the above, there is no ethical calling more expedient than the call to all men and women of goodwill and sound conscience to protect the wellbeing of all life forms on the earth and to speak on behalf of the future generation of human and non-human species-bio-diversity. The ethical obligation that arises from the devastation of nature owing to development-related activities of man, is, how ought we to live with the earth? (Harold Wilson, 2001.). The philosopher ought to remind humanity that nature has its life and as such man's relationship with nature in his dire quest for development should be charitable and sensitive. Although, nature has an instrumental value to man, however, its intrinsic worth is more essential and categorical. If the immediate goal of human life is to live happily on earth, development should not cause man swift happiness and perpetual misery. Man's right to development should not be at the expense of the other billions of lives which also have right to exist on earth. Respect for biodiversity preserves nature home to man for present and future generations. In his aggressive drive for development through science and technology, man must not parochially and senselessly mortgage the existence and wellbeing of future generations just for his swift happiness.

These indeed are the tasks and thrust of philosophy of development. Being an interdisciplinary course, it is critical, reflective, analytic, expository, evaluative and normative. It reflects on the basic assumptions and propositions of the theories of development, critically analyses them to reveal their underlying facts and their philosophical basis. It reflectively interrogates the reasonableness of these theories by offering critical evaluation to ascertain whether in the bid to pursue aggressive development, various nations and their people adhere to the principle of fairness, solidarity and subsidiarity. Finally, it prescribes certain principles as norms that each nation must imbibe to foster genuine, integral, healthy and sustainable development in order to foster a just and good national and transnational trade relations.

Therefore, philosophy of development is both ideological and a crusade. It is ideological because it represents principles of integral development. It is a cru-

sade in the sense that it advocates for a type of development that is just, built on the principles of solidarity and subsidiarity, intergenerational responsibility, charity and eco-friendliness, and eco-centrism and sustainability. It canvases for global justice amongst humans (peoples and nations) and for the comity of biodiversity.

In a word, philosophy of development is a philosophy that propagates the gospel of an integral progress and advancement of human existence, a development that improves the quality and standard of human life in accordance with the ontological essence of man both as a social, political, cultural and religious animal. It is a philosophy that discourages a situation where the rich (whether as individuals or as a country) gets richer and the poor do not only get poorer but snowballs to the level of abjectness and penury.

In other words, philosophy of development is the philosophy that employs philosophical periscope to discern what sort of development is desirable for the genuine advancement of human existence, survival and flourishing. It is a philosophy that views the harmonious improvement of the hypostatic nature of man as a genuine development. Philosophy of development is a critical quest for not just mere advancement but desirable advancement of the fortune and conditions of man's living on the society. And desirable development is that which tackles both the material and immaterial goods of man. Foremost in the agenda of philosophical studies in development is the critical examination of assumptions, claims and philosophical undertones of various theories of development giving accounts of the transformations that have taken place in time in national and transnational planes.

Conclusion

The foregoing discourses on philosophy of development have been based on the critical and systematic attempt to conceptualize what philosophy got to do with development. It has been lucidly established that the very notion of philosophy of development presupposes two basic assumptions-first that philosophy has essential business relationship or affinity with development; second that philosophy has the competence to critically and normatively interface and postulate on development. Ultimately, the goal of philosophy of development is to assert in line with the nature and essence of man in the society the categorical imperative of integral and sustainable development. Moreover, this paper has established that philosophy of development combines imports from environmental philosophy and environmental ethics to normatively and deductively establish what should constitute the right approach to development. This approach is considered in two capacities: man's relationship with fellow men (the relationships between nations) and man's attitude or disposition towards other members of the comity of biodiversity. Philosophy of development is a critical quest for not just mere advancement but desirable advancement of the fortune and conditions of man's living on the society. And desirable development is that which tackles both the material and immaterial goods of man. Therefore, to advance an integral development of man

and society; philosophy must be reverentially appealed to as a competent tool for authentic development.

References

1. Alafen, A. F. (2018), *Environmental Domestication or Degradation: The Moral Issues in Man's Relation with His Environment*, Ado-Ekiti: A Seminar Paper Submitted to the Department of Philosophy, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Award of Doctor of Arts Degree (PhD) in Philosophy.
2. Blyden, Edward, (1955), *The Negro in Ancient History; in the People of Africa: A Series of Papers on Their Character, Condition and Future Prospects*.
3. Edeh, Emmanuel. (1985), *Igbo Metaphysics*, Chicago: Loyola University Press.
4. Emeh, Ikechukwu Eke Jeffrey, (2013), "Dependency Theory and Africa's Underdevelopment: A Paradigm Shift from Pseudo-Intellectualism: The Nigerian Perspective", *International Journal of African and Asian Studies - An Open Access International Journal*, Vol.1.
5. Fanon, Franz. (1965). *The Wretched of the Earth*, London: Macgibbon & Kee.
6. <https://content.sciendo.com/view/journals/zireb/21/1/article-p67.xml>
7. <https://content.sciendo.com/view/journals/zireb/21/1/article-p67.xml>
8. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/sustainable-development>
9. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/sustainable-development>
10. <https://www.un.org/press/en/2019/sgsm19468.doc.htm>
11. Igbafen, M. L. (2014). *Core Issues and Theories in Philosophy of Development*, Ekpoma: AInno Printing Press.
12. Jacob, C. (2020) *The Values of Philosophy to Developmental Studies*, Kaduna: De Yung Printing Press.
13. Nwinya Steve, (2018), *The Significance of the Nigeria Philosophical Association's Biennial Conference at Ebonyi State University (NPA-EBSU 2018)*, Unpublished Article, Department of Philosophy and Religion, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki.
14. Rodney, W. (1990), *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa*, London: Boglelou Venture Publication.
15. Stumpf, S., (1971), *Philosophy: History and Problems*, America: McGraw-Hill Inc.
16. Uzomah, M. and Folorunso, P. O. (2020), "Globalization: An Inexorable Phenomenal Force, *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation, (IJHI)* Vol. 3, No. 2.
17. Uzomah, M. M. (2018), *Fundamental Issues in Philosophy and Development*, Kafanchan: De- Young Printing Press.
18. Uzomah, M. M. Isanbor P. O. & Uzomah C. S. (2023). "African Tech Development: The Ideal and Summit of Contemporary African Philosophy and Literary Studies". *African Social Sciences and Humanities Journals*, 4(1). 23-36. <https://doi.org/10.57040/asshj.v4i1.351>
19. Uzomah, Michael Maduawuchi and Paul Olorunsola Folorunso, (2022), *Theories and Philosophies of Development*, Kaduna: All-Well Printing and Publishing Co.,